

PHILOLOGICAL SCIENCES

OVER THE SEMANTIC TRANSITION OF SOME RELIGIOUS PHRASEOLOGICAL UNITS IN THE SPANISH LANGUAGE TO THE TERMINOLOGICAL SYSTEM

Aliyeva R.

University of Languages of Azerbaijan
Baku, Azerbaijan

Baku, 134 Rashid Behbudov str. AZ 1000

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.11114248>

Abstract

Several studies about the transition of phraseological units to the terminological system have shown that the phraseology and terminology which seem irrelevant and contradictory to each other are actually closely related. Terminology usually consists of a lexical category with limited use and nonfigurative language. Phraseology, on the other hand, is made up of a number of expressions that are widely used and have figurative meaning. It is an undeniable fact that both fields enrich each another. One can note the integration of the phraseological and terminological systems in the term formation process and said process occurs thanks to usage of units which already exist in a language with linguopragmatic adequacy without adding the new ones. The types of terminology based on semantic change are distinguished by their expressiveness, emotionality and stability. By means of the examples given in this article, we will be able to detect that the usage of the religious phraseological units in the Spanish language expands by integrating with the terms that belong to different fields and this process takes place thanks to the internal capabilities of the language. However, it's an undeniable fact that, the phraseological units which switch to terminological system compromise to some extent their expressiveness and style. This process is observed not only in Spanish, but also in other languages.

Keywords: terminology system, discourse, phraseology, expressivity, precedent onym

When we approach from a different perspective to the componential analysis of the religious phraseological units in the Spanish language, we can note various interesting, but unfortunately not quite researched processes in the linguopragmatic conditioning of the expressions with precedent onyms and their semantic evolution in the following stage. Among the processes that captured our attention, we can especially emphasize the great role that the religious phraseological units in Spanish language plays in enrichment of various fields of terminology.

N.N. Pickup, who studied the interrelation between terminological and phraseological units, points out in his research: *"In the classical sense, the terms portray the neutral class which has an individual and limited processing area of the lexicon and doesn't have a figurative meaning. However, observing the term-formation process makes us to think about the integration of terminological and phraseological units"* [1, p.138-140]. Such integration process directly turns out to be the logical conclusion of the processes that take place on the basis of the pragmatics in language and it happens thanks to the usage of units that already exist in the language with linguo-pragmatic adequacy, without having to add up new ones. S. A. Sasanina, who evaluated the pragmatic potential of the interaction between Terminology and Phraseology, was right when he said that *"the pragmatic information of the text makes it possible to determine the pragmatic communicative context... The meaning of the phraseological unit (the one that is related to terminology) is revealed in a pragmatic context"* [9, p.157]. The analysis of the facts about the usage in terminology of the biblical phrases and generally speaking, the religious phraseological

units in Spanish language lets us draw conclusions that they play an important role in the verification of the semantic capacity of context.

"Esta enfermedad recibió los nombres de "fuego sagrado", "mal de los ardientes", "fuego infernal" o "fuego de San Antonio" [29, p.74]. El ergotismo, denominado en el uso coloquial como "fiebre de San Antonio", "fuego de San Antonio" o "fuego del infierno", es una enfermedad causada por la ingesta de alimentos contaminados por mico toxinas (toxinas producidas por hongos parásitos), o por abuso de medicamentos que contengan esta misma sustancia [21].

Exactly the context helps us to comprehend the expression *"fuego de San Antonio"* not in a metaphorical, but terminological way. It should be recalled that, in the etymological sense, a special type of food poisoning, of which gangrene is an accompanying symptom was related to the treatment of *ergotism* [12] in the Middle Ages under the auspices of the representatives of The Order of Saint Anthony. And Saint Anthony is considered as the patron saint of "fire prevention" in history.

It is obvious that, *"the phraseological system of a language embodies such a multilayered system that its components have unique structural-semantic features and characteristic aspects"* [7, p.119-122]. In this regard, it is not possible for the transition of multiple Spanish religious phraseology, specifically, a certain number of precedent onyms to the terminological layer to not attract one's attention. Y.A. Krylov, who studied structural and discursive features of anthroponyms in Spanish, has mentioned that many of the religious phraseological units with precedent onym of Spanish like *"lira de Davis, síndrome de la mujer de Lot, síndrome de Lot, nuez de Adán, manzana de Adán, mal*

de San Roque, mal de San Benito, mal de San Mauro, mal de San Juan, enfermedad de San Lupo, fiebre de San Antonio/ fuego de San Antonio” have been successfully utilized in medical terminology.

Let's pay attention to the functional positions of some of them:

La nuez de Adán es una pequeña estructura semicircular que es más prominente en la parte delantera de la garganta de un hombre [27], la prominencia laríngea (popularmente conocida como nuez de Adán, manzana de Adán) es una protuberancia o abultamiento ubicada en la parte delantera del cuello y formada por la articulación de las dos láminas del cartilago tiroideas que rodea la laringe [35].

The phraseological units such as “*nuez de Adán*” that we encounter in the previous examples stand for “laryngeal prominence” or “thyroid cartilage protrusion” in Spanish and the first one of this expressions, the one that means “Adam's apple” in literal translation, is almost widely used as a medical term.

“...Porque es a esa parte que sobresale, y por tanto visible, a la que conocemos como nuez de Adán...Tanto los hombres como las mujeres tenemos cartilago tiroideas, o “nuez de Adán” [37].

The phraseological unit “*manzana de Adán*” which signifies “Adam's apple” has a high frequency of use as an alternative medical term.

En cuanto a las mujeres, el crecimiento de la manzana de Adán suele ser causa de un desequilibrio hormonal, genético o de deformación menor durante la adolescencia, algunas mujeres pueden sentirse abrumadas o afectadas en su autoestima por ello, pero existen tratamientos quirúrgicos que ayudan a reducirla [34]. La manzana de Adán es una pequeña estructura semicircular, que es más prominente en la parte delantera de la garganta de un hombre y que se mueve al tragar [28].

Intriguingly, even though “Adam's apple” isn't widely used in the medical terminology of Azerbaijani, it has limited functionality in medical media discourse under the influence of international terminology. *The thyroid gland sits beneath the cartilage on the front of the neck which is called “Adam's Apple” [21].* However, as a phraseological unit, the expression “Adam's apple” in our language stands for “the thing that makes a man to commit a sin” and it has played a part in the appearing of other medical terms (of which we will talk about later) such as “Complejo de Adán”, “Complejo de Adán y Eva”.

According to the statement of Y.A. Nikulina, one of the researchers who conducted a systematic study of the legal terminology and phraseology according to their semantic-functional characteristics formed on the basis of phraseological units, the types of terms that are formed of the semantic transition have their own sense of expressiveness, emotionality and at the same time stability. Furthermore, the main difference between these units and the other phraseological ones is that, although the phraseological units with similar structure embody stable compounds with a complex (metaphorized – R.A.) semantic capacity, “old phraseological units” that have already moved to the terminological

base can reflect a scientific concept [4, p.3]. Specifically, the possibility of using the phraseological units such as “*nuez de Adán*” and “*manzana de Adán*” as medical terms, proves that these units can also have terminological meaning. In other terms, such phraseological-terminological units in Spanish that are used in medical or media discourse have a meaning far from being directly related to the etymological basis of the expression. It is worth recalling that, this phraseological term expression has an analogous terminological status in Russian (*Адамово Яблоко*), English (*Adam's apple*) and in French (*pomme d'Adam*) and it is etymologically based on the “Bible”. In “Bible” it is said about that apple: *Y mandó Jehová Dios al hombre, diciendo: De todo árbol del huerto podrás comer; 17 más del árbol de la ciencia del bien y del mal no comerás; porque el día que de él comieres ciertamente morirás. (Génesis 2:16-17) [22].* Although the phraseological units like “*nuez de Adán*” or “*manzana de Adán*” used for an example are not directly related to “the first human sin” semantics, they reflect a new terminological meaning based on the metaphorical transition. I.e. the metaphorical implication “chain” is divided into two parts: **1.** Anatomical concept (oval shaped laryngeal prominence), **2.** The phraseological “version” of that concept (The oval-shaped fruit stuck in Adam's throat, that is, the apple of sin).

Expressions like “*complejo de Adán*” or “*complejo de Adán y Eva*” can be used as an example for the terminological denomination related to the “first sin” that Adam committed.

Y. A. Krylov has stated that the phraseological units which have acquired a terminological status in Spanish language like “*deficiencia de Adán*” and “*complejo de Adán*” have occupied a stable place in medical terminology and the first expression is andropause (Adam lives 930 years, according to the Bible), the second one means “*symptoms of dysfunction of a manager who considers it important to put his personal “label” on everything around him and considers himself a primary human being*” [8, p.237]. However, whether these examples or the explanations about this expression in Spanish media make it possible to say that Y.A.Krylov's concept isn't totally right and the expressions “*Complejo de Adán*” or “*Síndrome de Adán*” can be also interpreted as “the act of putting the blame on someone else when a man commits a sin but finds it difficult to admit”. More specifically, we can see in the first example below that this phraseological unit has the meaning of “psychological complex of a manager” and in the second one it characterizes the psychological state of “refusing to confess guilt”.

Me gustan este tipo de espacios en los que como sociedad planteamos los retos para los próximos 4 años de gobierno. Ojalá que nadie tenga en octubre Complejo de Adán: a empezar todo desde cero [24]. Juan Manuel Santos no escapa a este comportamiento, conocido como el complejo de Adán [15].

Anoche te hablé un poco de lo que yo he dado en llamar “el Síndrome de Adán”. Me refiero a la tendencia que tenemos los seres humanos a desviar la atención de la responsabilidad de nuestros errores por medio de revertir su culpabilidad en otros [19].

The roots of the second meaning go back to the instinct of self-preservation which is one of the traits of the human psyche. According to the famous research of Anna Freud, "The Ego and The Mechanisms of Defense", Sigmund Freud, the father of psychoanalysis has mentioned that the human uses a special type of defense mechanism - "repression" - in order to keep disturbing or threatening psychological thoughts from becoming conscious [11, p.17]. Among the courage of a person that is coping with a guilt complex to face the consequences of their actions and the defense mechanisms used by them when they can't morally deal with those consequences comes the attempt to blame others in order to deflect responsibility for their actions off themselves. Taking the example of Adam and Eva, who committed the "original sin" of human history, we can observe more specifically that Adam in his conversation with God tried to avoid the responsibility of tasting the forbidden fruit. 11. *Y Dios le dijo: ¿Quién te enseñó que estabas desnudo? ¿Has comido del árbol de que yo te mandé no comieses?*

12. *Y el hombre respondió: La mujer que me diste por compañera me dió del árbol, y yo comí (Génesis 3:11-12) [23].*

In Spanish, it can be determined that the second meaning is used more often: *Lo vivido estas semanas me ha recordado una enseñanza de antiguos sacerdotes que referían que uno de los primeros defectos de la raza humana que aparece en la Biblia es el llamado "complejo de Adán": consumada la desobediencia al proyecto de Dios, cuando es interpelado por el Creador, Adán dice: "Fue Eva", se defiende proyectando en ella toda la responsabilidad del pecado [18]. S.A. Mazayev, who studied the "Adam complex", did research about the guilt complex known in family psychology paying attention to an interesting part in "Bible" and stated that the reason why Adam tried to hide from God was that he no longer could conceal his sin from him and wanted to get away from the environment that reminded him of the sin that he committed [3]. Actually, it says in "Bible": *Y oyeron la voz de Jehová Dios que se paseaba en el huerto, al aire del día; y el hombre y su mujer se escondieron de la presencia de Jehová Dios entre los árboles del huerto (Génesis 3:8) [23].**

It should be noted that, the forbidden "fruit of the tree of knowledge of good and evil" which Adam and Eva ate made them to see the weight of their sin and feel ashamed when they became aware of their nakedness [2, p.345-355]. 7. *Entonces fueron abiertos los ojos de ambos, y conocieron que estaban desnudos; entonces cosieron hojas de higuera, y se hicieron delante de Dios [23].* As a side note, it was this time when another phraseological unit with precedent onim appear: "en traje de Adán" or "en traje de Adán y Eva", that is "naked". Although that expression doesn't have a wide range of functionality in the terminological system, it has a high frequency of use as a phraseological unit in modern Spanish: *Endiablado se pasea en traje de Adán [20]; Raúl Zuazo evalúa salir en "traje de Adán" para película de horror [39].* It can be seen that another version of the same phraseological unit in Spanish, *en traje de Adán*, is also widely used: *Fiestas en traje de Adán*

y Eva la llevan en Argentina. Pasar lo bacán con los amigos, bailando como el Pulento los mandó al mundo, es la nueva tendencia en Bifelandia [32].

"Síndrome de Job" can also be an example of the religious Spanish phraseological units that switched to the terminological system. This expression is based on the hardships of Prophet Job written in the "Bible", more specifically, the skin-eating disease that he was afflicted and it is used as a medical term in modern Spanish. *¿Qué es el Síndrome de Job? El síndrome de Job es conocido también con el nombre síndrome de hiperinmunoglobulina E. Responde a una infección del tipo estafilocócica, recurrente, por causa de un efecto genético que trae consigo un incremento altísimo de anticuerpos, entre ellos la inmunoglobulina [36].* In a section of the "Old Testament" where the life of Prophet Job is written - Libro de Job (Book of Job) it is said: 7. *Entonces salió Satanás de la presencia de Jehová, e hirió a Job con una sarna maligna desde la planta del pie hasta la coronilla de la cabeza [26].* The moment of Job's serious illness that tested his faith was the one that played an important role in the formation of an alternative nominative unit of immune disease which has a similar description. The illness which is known in the international-scientific terminology as "Buckley syndrome" – with the name of the scientist that has described it for the first time, is mostly presented as a phraseological unit-term containing the name of the "Bible" character in Spanish media discourse (*El síndrome de hiperinmunoglobulina también se conoce como síndrome de Job. Se le denomina así por el personaje bíblico Job, cuya fe fue puesta a prueba por una aflicción de úlceras y pústulas que supuraban [40]*), as well as in medical literature (*Lo denominaron "Síndrome de Job" haciendo alusión al personaje bíblico del Antiguo Testamento que sufría de lesiones cutáneas recurrentes [14]*).

As another medical term referring to the phraseology based on the "Bible" we can highlight the expression of "mal de San Lázaro". *Motivo por el que la lepra fue llamada "mal de San Lázaro", puesta bajo la advocación de este santo [33], La Lepra, también conocida como Enfermedad de Hansen o Mal de Lázaro, es una enfermedad infecciosa que se puede curar, sin dejar ninguna huella [17].*

As can be seen, this phraseological unit is based on the precedent-onim used in "El rico y Lázaro" (The Rich Man & Lazarus) of "The Gospel of Luke" (Evangelio de Lucas). 19 *Había un hombre rico, que se vestía de púrpura y de lino fino, y hacía cada día banquete con espléndidez. 20 Había también un mendigo llamado Lázaro, que estaba echado a la puerta de aquél, lleno de llagas, 21 y ansiaba saciarse de las migajas que caían de la mesa del rico; y aun los perros venían y le lamían las llagas. (Lucas 16: 19-21) [31].* According to that story, the beggar named Lazarus goes to heaven when he dies, but the rich man who didn't help him goes to Hell. Although the story talks about the poor beggar, the phraseological unit in Spanish "mal de San Lázaro" based on the story, was formed on a certain confusion, based on the leprosy of the man, which is stated in Jose Neira Ramirez's study [38, p.150], as

well as, in other sources in Spanish. *Los enfermos tenían la enfermedad de San Lázaro y eran llamados enfermos con el "Mal de San Lázaro". Así a los primeros hospitales o casas que cumplieron estas funciones se les llamaron Hospitales de San Lázaro o lazaretos, también llamados leproserías* [33].

For instance, the phraseological unit in Russian «петь Лазаря» that is based on the same story doesn't refer to his illness, but to the fact that he is poor and a beggar [5] and signifies "poverty and begging, persistently asking for financial assistance, exploiting" [6].

The formation of this term which is frequently used in modern Spanish as a scientific alternative of leprosy makes us agree with the statement of Y.I. Trubayeva who has made a research about the phraseological units becoming terms. As the philologist rightly points out, comprehending the transition of that type of phraseological units to the terminological system, i.e. the level of comprehension of the society plays an important role in here. It is on this basis that the phraseological unit gradually starts to transition to the terminology [10, p.204-206]. Exactly the process of gradual semantic transition provided semantic correlation of the term "lepra" (leprosy) with the phraseological unit "mal de San Lázaro". *"En el siglo XII, se creó una orden religiosa militar con la denominación de San Lázaro, para el cuidado de los leprosos, puesto que se denominaba entonces a la lepra como "mal de San Lázaro"* [16].

It should be noted that, the presedent onym in this expression played a role in the formation of another medical phraseological term *lazareto* (infirmary). *Un lazareto es un hospital o edificio similar, más o menos aislado, donde se tratan enfermedades infecciosas* [30]. The examples given not only reveals the important role that the religious phraseological units in Spanish play in the enrichment of different fields of terminology, but also allows to determine the accomplishment of the universal semantic transition processes. As Y. A. Yuryeva mentioned, the phraseological units lose their primary expressiveness inevitably during the transition process. However, the terms (i.e. the terms that are based on phraseological units – R.A.) obtain a wider range of functionality not only in scientific style, but also in colloquial style, by losing their conceptuality and monosemy [13, p.18].

As a result, it can be seen that the process of transition of phraseological units to the terminological system occurs thanks to the internal capabilities of the language and it happens not only in Spanish, but also in other languages as well.

Referencs:

1. Зеркина, Н. Н. Терминология и фразеология // - Челябинск: Вестник ЧГУ, Филология, Искусствоведение, - 2013. № 31 (322). - с. 138-140.
2. Иванов, М. С. Грех первородный / Православная энциклопедия. Под ред. Патриарха Московского и всея Руси Кирилла: [в 56 томах]. - Москва, т. 12. - 2011. - с. 345-355. URL: <http://www.pravenc.ru/text/166457.html>

3. Мазаев, С.А. Адамов комплекс, 2013 URL: <http://www.pravoslavie.ru/59292.html>

4. Никулина, Е. А. Терминологизмы как результат взаимодействия и взаимовлияния терминологии и фразеологии современного английского языка: / автореферат диссертации кандидата доктора филологических наук / - Москва, - 2005, - 24 с.

5. Петь Лазаря / Энциклопедический словарь крылатых слов и выражений / Под. ред. Вадима Серова. - Москва: Локид-Пресс, - 2005. - 852 с.

URL: <http://bibliotekar.ru/encSlov/15/38.html>

6. Петь Лазаря / Фёдоров А.И. Фразеологический словарь русского литературного языка / Фёдоров А.И. - Москва: Астрель, АСТ, - 2008. - 828 с. URL: <http://phraseology.academic.ru/>

7. Пикуль, С.Ю. Типология испанских фразеологизмов, содержащих числительное // Воронеж: Вестник ВГУ, Серия: Лингвистика и межкультурная коммуникация, 2010. №2, - с.119-122.

8. Рылов, Ю. А. Системные и дискурсивные свойства испанских антропонимов / Рылов Ю. А. - Воронеж: Издательство ВГУ, - 2010. - 390 с.

9. Сасина, С.А. Прагматический потенциал фразеологических единиц профессионального и терминологического происхождения в английском и русском дискурсах // Адыгей: Вестник Адыгейского государственного университета. Серия 2: Филология и искусствоведение, - 2008. - с. 156-159.

10. Трубаева, Е. И. Особенности терминологизации фразеологических единиц в современном английском языке // - Тамбов: Грамота, Филологические науки. Вопросы теории и практики, - 2015. № 12(54), - с. 204-206.

11. Фрейд, А. Психология Я и защитные механизмы / А.Фрейд. Москва: Педагогика- Пресс, - 1993. - 144 с.

12. Эрготизм (Ergotism) / Медицинские термины. - 2000. URL: <http://dic.academic.ru/dic.nsf/medic/8826>

13. Юрьева, Е.А. Терминологические единицы фразеологического происхождения в сферепрофессиональной коммуникации (на материале LSP страхования в английском языке): /диссертация кандидата филологических наук / - Москва, 2014. - 174 с.

14. Amada N. Síndrome de Hiper IgE: sus manifestaciones cutáneas. URL: <http://www.archivosdermato.org.ar/Uploads/125%20Sindrome%20HiperIge- Noriega.pdf>

15. Bonilla, M.E. El complejo de Adán // El Espectador. - 2012, 9 septiembre. URL: <http://www.elespectador.com/opinion/el-complejo-de-adan>

16. Cabello, D.M.E. Tablillas de San Lázaro. URL: <http://www.processionemisteritp.it/ciaccola/POSIBLE%20ORIGEN%20DE%20OLA%20CIACCOLA%20II%20Tablillas%20de%20San%20L%20C3%A1zar>

- o%20(2).pdf
17. Día Mundial de la Lucha contra la Lepra // Plataforma digital única del Estado Peruano. - 2013, 27 enero. URL: <https://www.gob.pe/institucion/minsa/campa%C3%BA99as/480-dia-mundial>
18. El complejo de Adán // La Voz. - 2013, 22 octubre. URL: <http://www.lavoz.com.ar/opinion/el-complejo-de-adan>
19. El síndrome de Adán (II) // 2010, 17 junio. URL: <https://ibvn.wordpress.com/2010/06/17/el-sindrome-de-adan-ii/>
20. Endiablado se pasea en traje de Adán // Diario Extra. -2015, 26 agosto. URL: <http://www.diarioextra.com/Noticia/detalle/268233/en-diablado-se-pasea-en->
21. Ergotismo URL: <https://es.wikipedia.org/wiki/Ergotismo>
22. Génesis 2 URL : <https://www.biblegateway.com/passage/?search=G%C3%A9nesis+2&version>
23. Génesis 3
URL : Génesis 3:8-10 RVR1960 - Y oyeron la voz de Jehová Dios que se - Bible Gateway
24. Giraldo, R.A. Complejo de Adán // El Colombiano. - 2015, 19 mayo. URL: <http://www.elcolombiano.com/opinion/columnistas/complejo-de-adan-GG1945866>
25. Hyperimmunoglobulin E syndrome URL: https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Hyperimmunoglobulin_E_syndrome
26. Job 2 URL: <https://www.biblegateway.com/passage/?search=Job+2&version=RVR1960>
27. La Función de la manzana de Adán URL: <https://www.amhasefer.com/q8kyKQvR/>
28. La Manzana de Adán, más que una simple protuberancia // El Nuevo Diario. - 2017, 15 diciembre. URL: <https://www.elnuevodiario.com.ni/suplementos/hombre/449694-manzana>
29. Laval, E. Sobre las epidemias del fuego de San Antonio// - Santiago: Revista chilena de infectología, - 2004. N o 21(1), - p. 74-76.
30. Lazareto URL: <https://es.wikipedia.org/wiki/Lazareto>
31. Lucas 16
URL: <https://www.biblegateway.com/passage/?search=Lucas+16&version>
32. Mac- Kay, M.T. Fiestas en traje de Adán y Eva la llevan en Argentina // La Cuarta. - 2016, 26 marzo.
URL: <https://www.lacuarta.com/mundo/noticia/fiestas-en-traje-de-adan-y->
33. Mal de San Lázaro // Enfermería avanza. - 2009, 2 agosto.
URL: <http://enfeps.blogspot.com/2009/08/mal-de-san-lazaro.html>
34. Manzana de Adán: por qué las mujeres no la tienen // Debate. - 2019, 22 Junio URL: <https://www.debate.com.mx/salud/Manzana-de-Adan-por-que-las-mujeres-no-la-tienen-20190622-0151.html>
35. Nuez de Adán URL: https://es.wikipedia.org/wiki/Nuez_de_Ad%C3%A1n
36. ¿Qué es el Síndrome de Job?
URL: <http://www.saluddiaria.com/3048/que-es-sindrome-job/>
37. ¿Qué es la nuez de Adán en realidad? - 2014, 12 marzo.
URL:<http://enroquedeciencia.blogspot.com/2014/03/que-es-la-nuez-de-adan-en-realidad.html>
38. Ramírez, J.N. El Hospital de San Lázaro de Lima // Lima: Folia dermatol, - 2006. N o 17 (3), - p. 149-150.
39. Raúl Zuazo evalúa salir en ‘traje de Adán’ para película de horror // La República. - 2011, 11 diciembre.
URL: <https://larepublica.pe/tendencias/596763-raul-zuazo-evalua-salir-en-traje-de-adan-para-pelicula-de-horror/>
40. Síndrome de hiperinmunoglobulina E.
URL: <https://medlineplus.gov/spanish/ency/article/001311.htm>